

Synthesis of 2''-Azetidiones bearing 2,4'-Bithiazole Moiety as Possible Antibacterials

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Earlier, we reported the synthesis of Schiff bases and 4-thiazolidinones bearing 2,4'-bithiazole moiety having antibacterial activity¹. 2-Azetidinones (β -lactams) are known to possess various biological activities². Survey of literature reveals no report on the synthesis of 2-azetidiones bearing bithiazole moiety. We report here the synthesis of 2''-azetidiones bearing 2,4'-bithiazole moiety.

The compounds were tested for antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, *S. abony*, *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa* using cup-plate method in acetone medium (0.5% concentration) and the activity was compared with furazolidone⁴ as standard. Compounds 2 and 3 showed no activity against *E. coli* and *S. abony*; 3 were found more active than 2 against *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa* but both less active than the standard.

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillary and are uncorrected. The purity of compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 781 spectrophotometer, mass spectra on a AEI MS 902 spectrometer and nmr spectra on a FT-NMR (80 MHz) instrument.

(2,4'-Bithiazole)-2'-arylideneamino-4-aryl (1) were synthesised as reported earlier¹.

1''-[4-Aryl-(2,4'-bithiazol)-2'-yl]-4''-aryl-2''-azetidiones (2): A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol) and triethylamine (0.01 mol) was dissolved in dioxane (40 ml) and kept in an ice-bath. To it cold solution of acetyl chloride (0.01 mol) was added slowly at 0°, the mixture was stirred for 10-12 h and left overnight. The precipitated triethylammonium chloride was filtered off and dioxane was removed by distillation. Residue obtained was poured into water and the resulting solid was washed with water, dried and crystallised from benzene: 2a, m.p. 261°; b 183°; c 105°; d 201°; e 168°; f 172°;

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| a, X=Y=H | i, X=CH ₃ , Y=H |
| b; X=H, Y=Cl | j; X=CH ₃ , Y=Cl |
| c, X=H, Y=CH ₃ | k, X=Y=CH ₃ |
| d, X=H, Y=OCH ₃ | l; X=CH ₃ , Y=OCH ₃ |
| e, X=Cl, Y=H | m; X=OCH ₃ , Y=H |
| f; X=Y=Cl | n, X=OCH ₃ , Y=Cl |
| g; X=Cl, Y=CH ₃ | o; X=OCH ₃ , Y=CH ₃ |
| h; X=Cl, Y=OCH ₃ | p; X=Y=OCH ₃ |

g 170°; h 135°d; i 171°; j 151°; k 267°; l 144°; m 204°; n 196°; o 211°; p 172°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1710 cm^{-1} (C=O); f; M^+ 458, δ (80 MHz; CDCl_3) 4.2 (2H, d, CH_2), 6.5 (1H, t, CH) and 7.43–7.97 (10H, m, Ar, thiazole).

1''-[4-Aryl-(2,4'-bithiazol)-2'-yl]-4''-aryl-3''-chloro-2''-azetidinones (3): To a stirred mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and triethylamine (0.02 mol) in anhydrous benzene (60 ml), monochloroacetyl chloride (0.02 mol) was added and the stirring was continued for 5 h at 40–50°, then left overnight. The triethylammonium chloride precipitate was filtered off, washed with benzene and the filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure. The resulting solid was crystallised from benzene: **3a**, m.p. 180°; **b**

174°d; c 228°; d 168°; e 183°d; f 181°d; g 228°d; h 187°d; i 171°d; j 185°d; k 182°d; l 178°d; m 176°d; n 188°d; o 221°; p 191°d; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1700 cm^{-1} (C=O); **3b** M^+ 458, δ (80 MHz; CDCl_3) 4.1 (1H, s, CHCl), 6.3 (1H, s, CH) and 7.34–7.89 (11H, m, Ar, thiazole)

References

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